

Increasing the Visibility of Grey Literature Project Report

Revision History

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Glossary

Term	Meaning
APO	The Analysis & Policy Observatory is a free, open access public policy repository which collects grey literature. ¹
CCAT	Centre for Culture and Technology
COKI	Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative
digital preservation	Depositing a copy of a grey literature output to a repository is called digital preservation.
DOI	Digital Object Identifier ² - a unique persistent identifier for digital objects
ECRs	Early career researchers
Elements	Symplectic Elements is an institutional publications management system from Digital Science ³
espace	espace is Curtin University's repository, using DSpace by DuraSpace ⁴
Figshare	Figshare is a repository owned by Digital Science, a company whose other products include Symplectic Elements and Dimensions. ⁵ The repository https://figshare.com/ is free, and Figshare also offers a paid customisable institutional repository product. ⁶
grey literature	'Published and unpublished research, produced by government, academia, business and industry, that is not controlled by commercial publishers' ⁷
HASS	Humanities, arts and social sciences
Humanities Commons CORE	Humanities Commons is a non-profit network funded by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and Michigan State University. Their CORE repository was funded by the National Endowment for the Humanities' Office of Digital Humanities. ⁸
identifier	An identifier is a label used to uniquely name something, for example a URL or an ISBN. A persistent identifier such as a DOI will always point to a research output over time, even if the research output moves around within a repository. ⁹
MCT	Media Culture and Technology research theme
metadata	Information used to describe an item, which adds meaning and can make the item more findable ¹⁰
OA	Open access
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID ¹¹

¹ <https://apo.org.au/page/about-apo>

² <https://www.doi.org/>

³ <https://www.digital-science.com/product/symplectic/>

⁴ <https://duraspace.org/dspace/>

⁵ <https://www.digital-science.com/>

⁶ <https://knowledge.figshare.com/institutions>

⁷ <https://libguides.library.curtin.edu.au/c.php?g=863554&p=6191902>

⁸ <https://hcommons.org/about-humanities-commons/>

⁹ <https://www.ands.org.au/guides/persistent-identifiers-awareness>

¹⁰ <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/describing-information/metadata>

¹¹ <https://info.orcid.org/what-is-orcid/>

repository	A repository is an online space for researchers to create a record of their grey literature, and share a copy.
Zenodo	A research repository which is free for researchers from any discipline, and any country, to save their research outputs to. ¹² Zenodo is funded by the European Commission, CERN and the Arcadia Fund. ¹³

¹² <https://zenodo.org/>

¹³ <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

1 Introduction

Researchers in the School of Media, Culture, Art and Social Inquiry (MCASI) produce grey literature such as reports, working papers and blog posts in addition to journal articles and books. This grey literature has been influential, for example research from the Centre for Culture and Technology (CCAT) has contributed to the introduction of audio description by Australia’s public broadcasters.¹⁴ However, currently this grey literature does not consistently have a unique identifier (such as a DOI), and is spread across various websites of Curtin research groups.

The Chief Investigator of this project was Dr Lucy Montgomery, Professor of Knowledge Innovation at Curtin University. The co-investigators of this project were Professor Cameron Neylon, Professor Katie Ellis, and Niamh Quigley. This research project had approval from the Curtin University Human Research Ethics Office (HRE2021-0515-03) and was undertaken between November 2021 and March 2022. MCASI with CCAT funded this five-week research project.

1.1 Project goals

The three goals for this project were:

- Goal 1 – Grey literature description & storage
- Goal 2 – Education on sharing grey literature research outputs
- Goal 3 – Audit of existing grey literature

Goal	How this goal was met
Goal 1 – Grey literature description & storage	<p>Eight MCASI researchers were interviewed across two focus groups to find out more about their grey literature practices, opinions and needs. The findings are presented in this report. The deidentified focus group transcripts and focus group guide are available online:</p> <p>Focus group transcripts - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6122007</p> <p>Focus group guide - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6139781</p>
Goal 2 – Education on sharing grey literature research outputs	<p>A guide for researchers about saving and sharing grey literature was produced. The guide ‘Sharing research beyond academia: A guide to free repositories for researchers’ can be downloaded from https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6330620</p> <p>To share the project findings directly with researchers, a seminar was held on 30th March 2021 ‘Grey Literature Research Outputs: What are they, where are they, and are they valued?’. The slides from this presentation can be downloaded from https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6395351</p>

¹⁴ Centre for Culture and Technology, Curtin University. (2021). *Infographic: Audio description in Australia*. <https://audiodescriptionau.com.au/?p=943>

Goal	How this goal was met
Goal 3 – Audit of existing grey literature	<p>An audit was undertaken for a sample of MCASI researchers who work within the Media Culture and Technology (MCT) research theme. These researchers were separate to the focus group participants.</p> <p>This audit and recommended actions for specific grey literature are included in this report in Appendix B, 'Grey Literature Audit'.</p>

Table 1 – Project goals and how they were met

1.2 Report structure

This research report has the following structure:

- Project background
- Project findings (including audit findings)
- Insights and opportunities
- Conclusion
- Appendix A – Research project approach
- Appendix B – Grey literature audit

2 Background

This section explores what grey literature is and where it can be found. It then summarises some of the barriers, risks to, and benefits of sharing grey literature¹⁵.

2.1 Grey literature definition

Grey literature was defined at two grey literature conferences (Luxembourg in 1997 and New York City in 2004) as electronic and print information produced by academia, government, industry and business, and not controlled by publishers (White et al., 2013, p. 3). Some forms of grey literature are 'theses and dissertations, government documents, conference papers, white papers, blog and discussion posts, and press releases' (Mering, 2018, p. 238). Other forms of grey literature are posters, infographics, videos, podcasts and interview recordings. Grey literature provides a channel for researchers to share their findings with industry and government, and impact policy (GreyNet International, 2014).

2.2 Where grey literature is found

Grey literature can be found throughout the internet, including on research group websites, repositories and third-party websites such as WordPress websites.

Repositories can be institutional, subject-based or general. Institutional repositories store the research data and outputs of researchers at that institution only, while subject-based repositories store research data and outputs relating to a specific research area. General repositories such as Zenodo store the research data and outputs of anyone.

A number of institutional repositories are already collecting grey literature and sharing it as open access (Lawrence et al., 2015, p. 235; Tsunoda et al., 2017, p. 8). However, more effort is needed by libraries to preserve and curate grey literature (Lynch, 2017, p. 129), and formally include diverse grey literature in their collection policies (Marsolek et al., 2021, p. 59). Australia has a dedicated open access repository called the Analysis & Policy Observatory (<https://apo.org.au/>), which stores and shares research findings including grey literature.

2.3 Barriers to sharing grey literature

While many Australian researchers produce grey literature such as articles for industry association publications (Kingsley, 2020, p. 286), not all grey literature is made available as open access in a repository. One of the barriers reported by producers of grey literature in sharing this form of research output was a 'lack of time and resources' (Lawrence et al., 2014, p. 18). Other highly ranked barriers were privacy issues with the research outputs, and refusal from sponsors to give permission to publish (Lawrence et al., 2014, p. 18).

2.4 Risks to grey literature

Some grey literature is poorly described and not digitally preserved via an appropriate repository (White et al., 2013, p. 3). This is often the case if reports are made available via a website only. Content on websites is vulnerable to deadlinks and link rot, where over time the content becomes inaccessible because it has been moved or removed (Lawrence et al., 2014, p. 19). For example, the audit in this project found evidence of the following:

¹⁵ Parts of this literature review have been summarised from Quigley, N. (2021). Engagement with open access among Curtin University Humanities researchers: Exploring the perceptions of, and barriers to open access [Unpublished Master's thesis]. Curtin University.

- one deadlink, which was likely caused by a Curtin University website structure change (now fixed)
- one missing document (item 12 in Appendix B, Table 5)

Digitally preserving grey literature by storing it in a repository is essential so that research groups can ensure that research is available to the communities it relates to; and so that it remains findable and available in the long term.

2.5 Benefits of storing grey literature in a repository

Multiple benefits of storing grey literature in a repository exist for researchers:

- Grey literature that is stored in a repository is more visible to other researchers, industry, government and communities, with a potentially bigger impact (Kingsley, 2020, pp. 286–287; Simons & Richardson, 2013, p. 6)
- The use of a persistent identifier (for example a DOI) enables gathering of citation information about the grey literature. These persistent identifiers can also be used to track mentions via Altmetrics or Event Data (Kingsley, 2020, p. 287)
- Grey literature in repositories is digitally preserved and not vulnerable to disappearing from websites (Kingsley, 2020, p. 287)
- Authors have the ability to see statistics for grey literature views and downloads (Kingsley, 2020, p. 287)
- Credibility can be added to the grey literature by being stored in a university repository
- The grey literature can be updated if needed, and the DOI can point to the latest version
- Many repositories are indexed by Google, thus making grey literature more findable.

3 Project Findings

This project set out to explore the grey literature practices, opinions and needs of MCASI researchers. This section summarises key findings from focus groups with eight researchers (deidentified as P1 – P8) and an audit of a sample of grey literature outputs created by MCT researchers [Appendix B – Grey Literature Audit](#). The research questions are included in [Appendix A – Research questions](#).

3.1 Perceptions of grey literature

Grey literature is important because ‘it’s all about community engagement’ (P2) and ‘public education’ (P9), rather than ‘placating the ivory tower’ (P9). For P7, grey literature is ‘dissemination to non-academic audiences’, and P5 feels that grey literature ‘carries research findings out, that isn’t ... the peer reviewed traditional things’ (P5). Grey literature can also include talking about research indirectly, and ‘engaging with the public forum’ (P8). One participant raised the importance of keeping an open mind about the definition of grey literature types, so that researchers continue to experiment:

we need to keep playing and hopefully bringing more and more things so that that conduit from the ivory tower to the rest of the world grows rather than shrinks (P5)

However, there is confusion over exactly what grey literature is, with individuals having different interpretations (P2, P3). The promotion of research via blogs and social media is time-intensive, and ‘in some ways it also exhausts, it takes lots of academic labour and work’ (P3). Grey literature is ‘so much of what we do’, but ‘just is not displayed’ (P9). Some participants feel their grey literature is ‘valued unofficially’ by senior management (P4, P9). Others want more recognition of grey literature at an institutional level (P6, P7, P9), ‘there should be a real articulation that ... the institution values this stuff as much as the other stuff’ (P9). P2 and P3 feel that grey literature in English is more highly valued than grey literature in other languages.

The impact of grey literature

Grey literature can have a big impact, on both communities and the careers of researchers. The creation of grey literature was worthwhile for P9, and led to positive social impact in addition to a positive career impact:

... my biggest impact has been through that kind of a medium rather than through peer reviewed journal articles... (and) a much more effective use of my time, and value in terms of the social impact of that, than the ... traditional literature (P9)

P4 also experienced high impact from their grey literature on communities, policy and practice:

... they have a very high impact, quite prestigious in its own world ... In an industry world, thinking about impact on policy and practice, that’s as good as it gets. (P4)

However, P4 questioned how this impact is considered on an institutional level:

... when I think about what’s my highest impact work, a lot of it has been things like [grey literature types] that have gone out with [organisations] or things that have happened in connection with the world. And when the university thinks about what is high impact or what’s prestigious it’s in very different terms. (P4)

In addition to being impactful, grey literature can be accessible and timely. Some grey literature is written in a less academic style, and therefore more accessible and ‘speak to those people who aren’t able to understand that academic language and grammar’ (P3). P2 uses grey literature peer review to add to ‘the quality rather than ... the credibility (P2) of their research. Some participants see grey literature as suited to immediate dissemination, because it can be published while public discussion is happening (P2, P5). Grey literature on a specific topic led to other opportunities for P5, including further grey literature and an invited journal article. High views for some of their grey literature was experienced by P3, P5 and P9.

3.2 How MCT researchers are saving and disseminating grey literature (RQ1)

During focus groups, participants were asked about:

- The types of grey literature they have produced
- Where they disseminate their grey literature
- Where their grey literature is stored/preserved
- Who they have collaborating with on grey literature

<p>Types</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reports • position papers • working papers • white papers • policy submissions • education materials • news articles • media interviews • magazine articles • seminars (and their transcripts) • presentations • catalogues 	<p>Dissemination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • on personal websites • on email lists • on Facebook • on LinkedIn • on Twitter • with Head of School at Curtin University • via Curtin media relations • via research group • via research funder • with industry • in industry publications
<p>Storage/preservation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • research website on Curtin domain • research website not on Curtin domain • external repository • personal website • funder website 	<p>Collaboration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • collaboration with international organisations • collaboration with industry partners • collaboration with research groups • collaboration with community groups

Table 2 – Focus group findings on grey literature types, dissemination, storage and collaboration

Participants were asked for any best practice examples of researchers who create grey literature, and provided the following examples:

- [Sonja Livingstone](#) (LSE)
- [Impact of Social Sciences](#) (LSE)
- [Henry Jenkins](#)
- [Deborah Lupton](#)
- [Axel Bruns](#)
- [Australian Institute of International Affairs](#)

At the time of audit (see [Appendix B - Results of grey literature audit](#)), none of the grey literature outputs checked were available to download from Curtin University's institutional repository space. Nine of the grey literature outputs in this audit have a record in espace, but **the actual output is not available to download**. Institutional repositories generally perform a digital preservation function, meaning that they store and back up research outputs over long periods of time. This is especially important for grey literature, as it is inherently more vulnerable. However, **digital preservation is not provided as a feature of espace at Curtin University**.

Participants had experience of lost grey literature due to a lack of digital preservation. P2 recounted an incident where grey literature was lost because the website hosting it was accidentally not renewed, and P5 noted that 'lots of the ... early 2010 ... websites that were great repositories once are gone now' (P5). P5 also feels there is 'very little commitment to creating persistent archives for research projects' (P5) that are not on institutional websites at Curtin, while 'institutional websites are so unfriendly to hosting those things there that they almost force you not to' (P5). P7 intends to use their own personal funds to keep a project website online once project funding runs out. When asked about finding grey literature created by others, some participants use Google (P7 and P9), and P6 sometimes looks on association websites. The Curtin media relations team offers assistance with publicising research, and P7 and P9 have found them helpful with sharing grey literature.

3.3 Metadata important to researchers to describe grey literature (RQ2)

Participants were aware of grey literature relevant metadata such as DOIs, keywords, Creative Commons licenses and acknowledgements (P2, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8). However, the researchers in the focus groups were unaware of any specific guidelines to follow on metadata for grey literature. P5 feels that 'the institution should be better at saying yes, we're going to look after and curate things so that they can at least persist' (P5), and has experienced a lack of support in hosting grey literature and 'the proper provision of metadata' (P5).

Unique identifiers for grey literature are important, because they ensure that these outputs are stored with metadata about them, and are as findable as possible.¹⁶ P5 would like to be able to generate DOIs from espace. P4 found that getting a DOI and ensuring their grey literature was in ORCID 'created extra work ... and required extra thought', so that they could make their research outputs visible (P4). **In this project's audit of a sample of 18 grey literature outputs, none had a DOI and just two had an ISBN.**

¹⁶ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

3.4 Grey literature storage and dissemination needs of MCT researchers (RQ3)

All focus group participants identified ways that support for grey literature could be improved. These needs are presented here in the participants' own words, and reframed as opportunities in [Section 4 – Insights and Opportunities](#).

P2 feels that **guidance on grey literature storage and preservation would be useful**, including templates, metadata and DOI, but feels that change is 'more likely to come from the bottom up than the top down' (P2). P3 would like **more grey literature templates** and contacts, **guidance on which grey literature type is best for each audience** 'it's really difficult to find ... which one is the right one?' (P3). P4 would like grey literature **support with curation, typesetting and website maintenance for blogs**. P5 would like a **workflow for grey literature**, so they could 'put a report in, put a DOI on it, and get it automatically shipped into the APO so that it got national exposure' (P5). P6's previous university had guidelines and support in place, and has found 'coming to a place that has no guidelines or process or really support, it's hard and very different' (P6). P7 wants an 'uncomplicated and intuitive' (P7) process for storing and disseminating grey literature, and more support (P7):

I would like someone to help me put it in the place that it needs to go ... I just don't want that to be my job. Or I would like some support if it is my job. (P7)

P8 would like **more representation of categories suitable for grey literature in Elements**, as the current categories are 'so constricted' (P8) that they are a deterrent to adding grey literature. P9 feels that there are **no guidelines on how to share grey literature** and has been 'making it up as I go' (P9). They would like guidance on 'where I should be focusing my energies, how I should be getting my stuff out there' (P9), as well as incentives for producing grey literature.

3.5 Grey literature and Curtin systems

Participants discussed Curtin systems such as Elements and espace. One of the participants was frustrated that grey literature workflows and processes seem complicated:

I'm an exhausted academic, I have much to do ... other avenues are just unclear to me. You know, I'm sure I could put it in our library, but I don't cuz it seems complicated. (P7)

Concerns were also raised that Curtin systems are unable to show how the university values grey literature and creativity:

... there's really big problems at the moment in terms of fairness, and the fact that Curtin systems don't reflect how much the university actually values impact and how much it actually values grey literature and creativity among its researchers. (P4)

While P4 feels that 'Curtin values impact' (P4), P4 needs to purposefully communicate each new piece of grey literature to senior management because 'systems like Elements and espace are really broken' (P4). P5 feels that Curtin University wants to be able to show engagement and impact, but doesn't yet have the underlying infrastructure to support this.

We've shifted to the rhetoric around engagement and impact before there's been the scaffolding needed to support people in, not so much producing it, but seeing what happens after they do. (P5)

ORCID and grey literature

ORCID is recognised by some participants (P4, P5) as a useful identifier for researchers, and an important system as part of recording and disseminating grey literature:

And the other half of the problem, which is, how do you make this stuff easy to navigate, and easy for university systems to interface with is where the challenge has been. (P4)

However, P5 is frustrated about having to perform data entry multiple times due to a lack of integration between Curtin systems and ORCID:

...the fact that our institution currently isn't pulling from ORCID, does my head, why the hell are we populating it four times when we really do have a way to do it once? (P5)

Elements and grey literature

One participant advocates for adding all grey literature to Elements because their 'view is play the game and show them how productive we actually are' (P9). However, P8 felt the Elements categories were 'so constricted' for grey literature, that P8 was 'not even going to try' to add grey literature to Elements (P8). P6 feels that the current messaging around Curtin systems (such as Elements and espace) is that the users of these systems are the problem, not the systems:

I think that messaging to faculty is you have to use it. It's perfect if you can't use it you're the problem. And by the way, if you don't use it, you won't get promoted and you're a bad researcher. (P6)

P6 suggested a change to this messaging so that the limitations of these systems are acknowledged. P6 sees this as an opportunity to 'be honest about it as opposed to ... toxic positivity and making you feel like you're deficient' (P6).

3.6 Inequities for grey literature creators

Experiences recounted during focus groups suggest inequities for researchers who create grey literature, including publication expectations and the promotion process. Multiple participants were concerned about early career researchers (ECRs) who produce grey literature.

Publication expectations

When publishing research outputs, P4 acknowledged their privilege in being able to 'ignore the rules', where they keep producing grey literature even though it is not officially recognised by Curtin as a valued research output:

... there are some people who have sort of figured out that actually, I'm gonna keep doing this, the university will value it and I've got the kind of sense of entitlement and privilege that's just going to let me ignore the rules and do what I think is important and then tell you about it (P4).

P4 also feels that researchers who follow the rules can be at a disadvantage:

And then there are other researchers who see promotion guidelines, they see publication guidelines, they maybe aren't as familiar with the grey areas in universities, and so those people end up following the rules and feeling hugely disadvantaged and frustrated because that other information is all hidden information,

it's you know, information that some of us have privileged access to, and so we are engaging with the rules in different ways. (P4)

Researchers in some research areas may be less likely to get attention for their research outputs. P6 feels that some research topics are less attractive: 'there is very much a have and have not situation at Curtin when it comes to who can get attention and who can't' (P6). P6 wants 'equitable access to resources' (P6) for Faculty of Humanities researchers who produce grey literature, in order to facilitate promotion of their research.

Promotion process

Participants were asked how they feel their grey literature is valued during the promotion process. Some feel that the promotion system is inequitable for researchers who create grey literature. While preparing a promotion application, P4 found that their grey literature was not visible in Curtin systems. P4 felt that this could be a deterrent for researchers who produce grey literature:

If you know you've worked really hard and then Curtin systems don't talk to each other and they're completely broken. And you're told on a form that you need to demonstrate what you did using this type of report, it's possible for people to be completely put off applying for promotion by those broken systems... (P4)

While P4 acknowledged their privilege in advocating for the impact of their grey literature, they felt that the promotion process is inequitable for those without this privilege:

... that's a game that some privileged people get to play, but there are a lot of people who just get left out of the opportunity because our systems are broken and not transparent I think (P4)

During the promotion process, P7 feels that 'unless the grey literature actually has demonstrable impacts, it doesn't mean much' (P7). Because promotions committees include academics from different faculties, some 'don't necessarily understand ... what humanities research is, why this type of publication, for example, matters a lot (P7). P6 did not feel that grey literature was explicitly valued in the promotion process, because 'if it wasn't in Elements it didn't get in there' (P6). P2 continues to share their research via grey literature because 'it's influencing the world' (P2), and acknowledged their privilege in not being concerned about this 'affecting my opportunity for promotion or anything like that (P2).

Informal mentorship

One participant suggested that researchers who have mentors and informal advice from colleagues are in a better position to navigate the promotion process: 'the whole process to me just kind of felt like kind of blindly figuring it out and I happen to be lucky enough that you know I had the right people on that' (P9). P9 used systems outside of Curtin to prepare their promotion application. When asked if the advice on structuring their application was in the official promotion guidelines, P9 responded that 'most of the way I structured my promotion was through one-on-one discussions with colleagues' (P9). P9 expressed a concern that this informal mentorship is not available to all researchers:

I think a lot of people don't get that. And then they again just fall through the cracks. And as [P6] was saying, it becomes you know, an equity issue. And I think that the institution itself is not set up to do that ... It's very reliant on, you know, good-willed individuals, but the institution, while it makes all these ... claims to fairness ... like

everyone winning together. The reality is, it actually incentivizes a very dog eat dog situation, which grinds through a lot of people (P9)

When asked if the advice from informal mentors on how to structure a promotion application was reflected in the official promotion guidelines, P9 responded that ‘most of the way I structured my promotion was through one-on-one discussions with colleagues’ (P9).

P5 felt that a lack of mentorship and advice specific to grey literature could particularly disadvantage ECRs:

I can see that that's quite a difficult mind shift, but I also think for younger researchers where this is important, like as [participant name] says, for promotion and everything else, it really depends who your mentors and who your immediate culture is as to whether you think this matters or not (P5)

Further concern for ECRs was expressed by P3, P7 and P9, ‘... if someone like me feels like that then people first getting into it probably just have no clue where to put things’ (P7). P9 suggested that providing specific guidance and recognition of grey literature created by ECRs could also be beneficial:

‘having these ... clear pathways, these little touchstones that they can go, alright I can go for that. I can build a skill set here. I can get some recognized outputs here that I know the university is going to value’ (P9)

3.7 Audit findings

The audit found the following issues, and has recommended actions for each grey literature output included in the audit sample (see [Appendix B – Results of grey literature audit](#)):

- Multiple copies of the same grey literature file is online (with different filenames)
- Some of the grey literature has metadata in espace
- None of the grey literature sampled was available in espace to download
- Not all grey literature is shared with APO

4 Insights and Opportunities

Focus group participants provided many insights on what is preventing them from making more of their grey literature visible. This section summarises these insights as opportunities, along with the potential outcomes if the opportunities are adopted.

	Insight	Opportunity	Outcome
1	No guidelines available for storing and sharing grey literature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote the guide created in this project which includes advice on metadata, templates, uploading grey literature to repositories, and adding grey literature to ORCID records. 	More Curtin-created grey literature will be preserved, findable and visible in researchers' ORCID records
2	No straightforward method to get DOIs for reports	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote existing Library service to get a DOI Promote the guide which includes how to get a DOI from other repositories 	More Curtin-created grey literature will be preserved, findable and visible in researchers' ORCID records
3	No institutional support for archiving websites where funding has ended	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigate how project websites could be archived and maintained online with the assistance of Information Management and Archives/Digital & Technology Solutions 	Curtin-created grey literature will be preserved even after a project has ended
4	Element categories are not available for different types of grey literature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update Elements forms in consultation with researchers who produce grey literature so that the types correspond to what researchers are actually creating, and capture rich metadata. Elements to espace crosswalks may also need to be updated. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More metadata will flow through to espace, thus making well-described grey literature more findable¹⁷ outside of Curtin University e.g., in Google searches Upload and access statistics may be higher in espace, and usable in the promotions process

¹⁷ p8, Nicholson, S. W., & Bennett, T. B. (2021). Do institutional repository deposit guidelines deter data discovery? Evidence Based Library and Information Practice, 16(3), 2–17. <https://doi.org/10.18438/eblip29913>

	Insight	Opportunity	Outcome
5	Request from researchers for Curtin workflow that makes getting DOIs and sending to APO more automated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Future upgrades of espace could include the ability for researchers to mint their own DOI when they add grey literature to espace • Adding to APO is currently manual per researcher when they are logged in 	Potentially less intervention for researchers to get DOI for their grey literature if using espace as a repository
6	ECRs who create grey literature are at a disadvantage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide specific advice for ECRs on grey literature using the guide created in this project 	ECRs will be more confident in creating and sharing grey literature
7	Experiences of the promotion system suggest that it is inequitable for researchers who create grey literature. Additionally, researchers who have mentors and informal advice from colleagues may find it easier to navigate promotion than those who strictly follow the promotion guidelines.	<p>Clearer promotion guidelines are needed so that grey literature is recognised in the promotion process:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What types of grey literature & metrics can be included (for applicants) • What types of grey literature & metrics can be included (for promotion committees, especially those who do not have a Humanities background) • How grey literature can be represented in the engagement section 	Researchers who produce grey literature will be better prepared in the promotion process, and have equivalent opportunities as researchers who produce mainly journal articles
8	<p>Requests from participants for more guidance on the following grey literature topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which type is best for each audience • Who can provide expert support with e.g. illustrations, typesetting, website maintenance • Best practice examples 	<p>Future support for grey literature could include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which type is best for each audience • Curtin contacts for illustrators/typesetting/website maintenance • Best practice examples for multiple types of grey lit (both internal & external) 	Researchers will be more confident in creating and sharing grey literature

Table 3 – Insights, opportunities and their potential outcomes

5 Conclusion

Grey literature is vital for humanities researchers because it provides a way to engage with the communities they work with. Focus group participants are active in creating a variety of grey literature types, which they have found to be a successful and accessible way to impact communities, policy and practice. However, the researchers interviewed in focus groups lack clear guidelines around grey literature; have no straightforward method to get DOIs for reports; find Elements categories irrelevant; and have no institutional support for archiving websites where project funding has ended. While some participants feel that Curtin University values impact, this is not reflected in Curtin systems including Elements and espace.

The promotion process is inequitable for researchers who produce grey literature, and one participant felt that informal mentoring from colleagues was a significant factor in their ability to navigate the promotion process as a grey literature producer. Focus group participants were empathic towards ECRs who create grey literature, as these ECRs are considered to be at a disadvantage without the benefit of clear guidelines around grey literature.

The impact of these failings in systems, processes and workflows at Curtin University is that:

1. Researchers are using individual best practice in the absence of institutional guidelines about storing and sharing grey literature
2. Grey literature is not well-preserved or findable, and is especially vulnerable to being lost when project funding is finished
3. The promotion process does not formally recognise grey literature, thus putting these researchers at a disadvantage.

[‘Sharing research beyond academia: A guide to free repositories for researchers’](#) created as part of this project includes the following sections:

- How to get a DOI
- Repository options
- How to save research outputs to Zenodo
- How to save research outputs to Figshare or Humanities Commons CORE
- Examples and templates of metadata for your research outputs
- How to add research outputs to your ORCID record
- Tips for sharing your research outputs beyond academia

The guide fills some of the support gaps identified by focus group participants. However, there is scope to make grey literature more visible and formally acknowledge its impact, by considering the opportunities presented in this report.

Appendix A – Research Project Approach

Research questions

The research questions for this project were:

What actions can Curtin University take to enable its researchers to increase the visibility of their grey literature research outputs?

RQ1: How are MCT researchers currently saving and disseminating their grey literature?

RQ2: What metadata is important to describe grey literature?

RQ3: What grey literature storage and dissemination needs do MCT researchers have?

Data collection

Purposive sampling was used to invite focus group participants within MCASI who produce grey literature. Eight researchers were interviewed online using Microsoft Teams. Two focus groups were moderated by Niamh Quigley on 27/01/2022 and 01/02/2022, with approval from Curtin University’s Human Research Ethics Committee (HRE2021-0515-03).

Focus group 1	Focus group 2
4 participants (P2 – P5)	4 participants (P6 – P9)
P1 was an observer	P8 was an observer and a participant
1 hour and 6 minutes duration	1 hour and 8 minutes duration

Table 4 – Focus group details

Focus groups were auto-transcribed using Microsoft Teams built-in functionality. Following transcription review and correction, Niamh Quigley analysed the data with Braun and Clarke’s thematic analysis approach¹⁸ using the qualitative data analysis software, MaxQDA (<https://www.maxqda.com/>). The deidentified focus group transcripts and question guide are publicly available in the Zenodo repository:

- Focus group transcripts - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6122007>
- Focus group guide - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6139781>

¹⁸ Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>

Appendix B – Grey Literature Audit

Method

A sample of grey literature created by Media Culture and Technology researchers was assessed against multiple criteria:

- Persistent identifier – does the grey literature output have a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) or an ISBN
- Is there a record of the grey literature output in espace, but not including a copy of the grey literature output
- Is there a copy of the actual grey literature output in espace, as well as a record
- Is the grey literature output findable on another website, e.g. a Curtin research group website or an organisation connected to the report. (For this audit, ResearchGate and academia were not considered as reliable websites for hosting grey literature, as these are both for-profit academic networking websites.¹⁹)
- Is the grey literature output available on the APO website (either uploaded to APO or linked from APO)

The grey literature in this audit included reports, position papers, submissions to government and educational material.

The suggested actions specific to each grey literature output are presented in the Actions column of Table 1. Note that some of the actions listed below have already been taken. The issues found in this audit have been included in the project findings in this report (see [section 3.7 Audit findings](#)).

¹⁹ <https://osc.universityofcalifornia.edu/2015/12/a-social-networking-site-is-not-an-open-access-repository/>

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Results of grey literature audit

No.	Title	Year	DOI	ISBN	Record of grey lit in espace	Copy of grey lit in espace	Grey lit on website(s)	Grey lit in APO	Recommended actions
1	Smartphones and equal access for people who are blind or have low vision	2020	No	No	No	No	Yes ²⁰	Yes ²¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add report to Elements • Upload copy of report to espace via Elements • Change APO details to point to copy in espace
2	Audio description and Australian Television: A position paper	2018	No	No	Yes ²²	No	Yes ²³ (two filenames)	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload copy of report to espace via Elements • Remove one copy of report on Curtin websites • Submit to APO (with link to copy in espace)
3	Internet of Things (IoT): Education and Technology. The relationship between education and technology for students with disabilities	2018	No	No	Yes ²⁴	No	Yes ²⁵	Yes ²⁶	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload copy of report to espace via Elements • Change APO details to point to copy in espace • Change VOCEDplus details²⁷ to point to copy in espace

²⁰ <https://ccat.curtin.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/sites/33/2021/01/VisionAustraliaSmartphoneReportACC.pdf>

²¹ <https://apo.org.au/node/309879>

²² <https://espace.curtin.edu.au/handle/20.500.11937/69691>

²³ https://resources.curtin.edu.au/file/faculty/hum/ADPositionPaper_Alt-text-enabled.pdf and <https://ccat.curtin.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/sites/33/2018/06/ADPositionPaper.pdf>

²⁴ <https://espace.curtin.edu.au/handle/20.500.11937/69810>

²⁵ <https://www.ncsehe.edu.au/publications/internet-of-things-iot-education-and-technology-the-relationship-between-education-and-technology-for-students-with-disabilities/>

²⁶ <https://apo.org.au/node/134321>

²⁷ <https://www.voced.edu.au/content/ngv%3A79260#>

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No.	Title	Year	DOI	ISBN	Record of grey lit in espace	Copy of grey lit in espace	Grey lit on website(s)	Grey lit in APO	Recommended actions
4	Mainstreaming Captions for Online Lectures in Higher Education in Australia	2017	No	No	Yes ²⁸	No	Yes ²⁹	Yes ³⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload copy of report to espace via Elements • Change APO details to point to copy in espace • Consider submitting to VOCEDplus
5	Using smartphones to navigate urban spaces: People with disabilities and the role of mobile technologies in three WA locations	2017	No	No	Yes ³¹	No	Yes ³²	No	<p>This report is difficult to find online (in Google & Google Scholar):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload copy of report to espace via Elements • Submit to APO (with link to copy in espace)
6	Accessing Subscription Video on Demand: A study of disability and streaming television in Australia	2016	No	Yes	Yes ³³	No	Yes ³⁴	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload copy of report to espace via Elements • Submit to APO (with link to copy in espace)
7	Access and Barriers to Online Education for People with Disabilities	2016	No	No	Yes ³⁵	No	Yes ³⁶	Yes ³⁷	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload copy of report to espace via Elements • Change APO details to point to copy in espace • Change VOCEDplus details³⁸ to point to copy in espace

²⁸ <https://espace.curtin.edu.au/handle/20.500.11937/54569>

²⁹ https://www.ncsehe.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/MainstreamingCaptions_FinalReport.pdf

³⁰ <https://apo.org.au/node/127266>

³¹ <https://espace.curtin.edu.au/handle/20.500.11937/70858>

³² <https://humanities.curtin.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/sites/4/2018/06/FINALFinalSmartphone-report-changes-accepted.pdf>

³³ <https://espace.curtin.edu.au/handle/20.500.11937/56414>

³⁴ https://accan.org.au/files/Grants/VOD%20tip%20sheets/VOD%20Accessibility_report_web_accessible.pdf

³⁵ <https://espace.curtin.edu.au/handle/20.500.11937/55588>

³⁶ <https://www.ncsehe.edu.au/publications/access-and-barriers-to-online-education-for-people-with-disabilities/>

³⁷ <https://apo.org.au/node/63921>

³⁸ <http://hdl.voced.edu.au/10707/403257>

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No.	Title	Year	DOI	ISBN	Record of grey lit in espace	Copy of grey lit in espace	Grey lit on website(s)	Grey lit in APO	Recommended actions
8	People seeking asylum in Australia: Access and support in higher education	2018	No	No	Yes ³⁹	No	Yes ⁴⁰ (two filenames)	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload copy of report to espace via Elements • Remove one copy of report on Curtin website • After duplicate report removed, make sure links to report from here, here and here still work • Submit to APO (with link to copy in espace)
9	'In Search of Safety' Programme Evaluation: Final Report	2018	No	No	No	No	Yes ⁴¹	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add report to Elements • Upload copy of report to espace via Elements • Submit to APO (with link to copy in espace)
10	People Seeking Asylum and Higher Education in Australia: Post-National Symposium Report	2018	No	No	No	No	Yes ⁴²	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload copy of report to espace via Elements • Submit to APO (with link to copy in espace)
11	Submission on the Australian Citizenship Legislation Amendment (Strengthening the Requirements for Australian Citizenship and Other Measures) Bill 2017	2017	No	No	No	No	Yes ⁴³	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add submission to Elements • Upload copy of submission to espace via Elements • Add link to submission to Centre for Human Rights Education publication website

³⁹ <https://espace.curtin.edu.au/handle/20.500.11937/74907>

⁴⁰ https://www.ncsehe.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/Hartley_PeopleSeekingAsylum.pdf and https://www.ncsehe.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/Hartley_PeopleSeekingAsylum_FINAL.pdf

⁴¹ <https://humanrights.curtin.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/sites/27/2018/07/Red-Cross-In-Search-of-Safety-Final-Report-April-2018-FINAL.pdf>

⁴² https://humanrights.curtin.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/sites/27/2018/03/People-Seeking-Asylum-Higher-Edu_Post-Symposium-Report_March2018.pdf

⁴³ https://www.aph.gov.au/Parliamentary_Business/Committees/Senate/Legal_and_Constitutional_Affairs/CitizenshipBill2017/Submissions

Grey Literature – Project Report

No.	Title	Year	DOI	ISBN	Record of grey lit in espace	Copy of grey lit in espace	Grey lit on website(s)	Grey lit in APO	Recommended actions
12	Feedback on Proposals in Strengthening the Test for Australian Citizenship	2017	No	No	No	No	No ⁴⁴	N/A	<p>This feedback on proposals is not findable online:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add submission to Elements • Upload copy of submission to espace via Elements • Add link to submission to Centre for Human Rights Education publication website
13	Social Justice Simulations: Social Justice Exercise Manual	2016	No	No	Yes ⁴⁵	No	Yes ⁴⁶	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add manual to Elements • Upload copy of manual to espace via Elements • Link from Centre for Human Rights Education publication website to manual is broken – either point to manual on UQ or Curtin espace (once uploaded)
14	Social Justice Simulations: Social Justice Case Studies	2016	No	No	Yes ⁴⁷	No	Yes ⁴⁸	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add case studies to Elements • Upload copy of case studies to espace via Elements • Link from Centre for Human Rights Education publication website to case studies is broken – either point to case studies on UQ or Curtin espace (once uploaded)

⁴⁴ Submission not found on www.aph.gov.au but could be there

⁴⁵ <https://espace.curtin.edu.au/handle/20.500.11937/58322>

⁴⁶ <https://espace.library.uq.edu.au/view/UQ:553576>

⁴⁷ <https://espace.curtin.edu.au/handle/20.500.11937/58557>

⁴⁸ <https://espace.library.uq.edu.au/view/UQ:553578>

Grey Literature – Project Report

No.	Title	Year	DOI	ISBN	Record of grey lit in espace	Copy of grey lit in espace	Grey lit on website(s)	Grey lit in APO	Recommended actions
15	The regional impacts of Australian asylum seeker policies: what "stopping the boats" means for people seeking asylum	2016	No	Yes	No	No	Yes ⁴⁹	Yes ⁵⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add report to Elements • Upload copy of report to espace via Elements
16	Policy as punishment: asylum seekers in the community without the right to work	2014	No	No	No	No	No	Yes ⁵¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add report to Elements • Upload copy of report to espace via Elements
17	Submission to the Australian Human Rights Commission's National Inquiry into Children in Immigration Detention	2014	No	No	No	No	No ⁵²	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broken link⁵³ to submission from Centre for Human Rights Education publication website
18	Refugees in Western Australia: Settlement and Integration	2012	No	No	No	No	Yes ⁵⁴	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add report to Elements • Upload copy of report to espace via Elements • Add link to report to Centre for Human Rights Education publication website

Table 5 – Results of grey literature audit

⁴⁹ <https://socialsciences.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/Academy-Paper-6-2016-The-Regional-Impacts-of-Australian-Asylum-Seeker-Policies-final-UPDATED-JUL16-1.pdf>

⁵⁰ <https://apo.org.au/node/65849>

⁵¹ <https://apo.org.au/node/38122>

⁵² Could not find submission on <https://humanrights.gov.au/our-work/projects/commission-website-national-inquiry-children-immigration-detention>

⁵³ https://blogs.curtin.edu.au/human-rights-education/files/2014/06/HRC-submission_Enhanced-Screening-of-Children1.pdf

⁵⁴ https://library.bsl.org.au/jspui/bitstream/1/5051/1/FozdarF_Refugees-in-Western-Australia-settlement-and-integration_MMRCI-2012.pdf

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